

STUDY OF ACUTE DYSENTERY (SHIGELLOSIS): CLINICAL, EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, PATHOGENETIC, AND IMMUNOLOGICAL ASPECTS

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Abstract. *This article systematizes modern data on acute dysentery and the formation of scientifically grounded approaches to the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of the disease. Within the framework of a study aimed at examining acute diarrhea in children, 62 children undergoing treatment at Children's Infectious Diseases Hospital No. 4 in Tashkent were examined. We analyzed the clinical features of dysentery, taking into account the patients' age, the causative agent of infection, the type of feeding, and the state of intestinal microflora.*

Keywords: *acute intestinal infections, acute diarrheal syndrome, acute dysentery, Shigellosis.*

Introduction

Acute dysentery (Shigellosis) is one of the leading bacterial pathologies of the gastrointestinal tract and continues to have a significant impact on the epidemiological situation and socioeconomic development on a global scale [1,2,3]. Despite substantial progress in sanitation, hygiene, and antibacterial therapy, the disease continues to be registered both in developing countries and in economically developed countries [4,5,6,14]. According to estimated data from international epidemiological studies, tens of millions of cases of shigellosis are registered annually worldwide, with a significant proportion occurring among children under 5 years of age. Mortality remains highest in regions with limited access to medical care and clean drinking water [7,8,9,15].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), this phenomenon is among the leading factors causing disability and mortality among the population in three quarters of the countries of the world. The relevance of shigellosis-associated acute dysentery remains high, despite progress in preventive measures, clinical diagnostics, therapeutic approaches, and rehabilitation programs [4,5,10,11]. The above indicates the priority of this study and is currently an urgent task.

Research methods

Within the framework of a study aimed at examining acute diarrhea in children, 62 children undergoing treatment at Children's Infectious Diseases Hospital No. 4 in Tashkent were examined. We analyzed the clinical features of dysentery, taking into account the patients' age, the causative agent of infection, the type of feeding, and the state of intestinal microflora.

Research results and Discussion

Among the examined children under 3 years of age, 32% were infants in the first year of life, and 68% were children in the second year. The predominant type of feeding was mixed feeding (75.8% of cases, $P < 0.001$). The main route of transmission of infection was foodborne (88.1%, $P < 0.001$). Repeated episodes of dysentery were noted in the anamnesis of 12.5% of children. Most patients (46.7%) were hospitalized during the first three days of the disease,

whereas late hospitalization (days 4-7) was observed in 19.4% of cases. It is important to note that 12 of the examined children (19.4%) had a history of recurrent dysentery [12,13].

In general, more than half of the children (56%) were admitted to the hospital during the first week of illness, which made it possible to start diagnostics and therapy in a timely manner. The mean age of the patients was 14.0±8.34 years, with boys predominating.

Analysis of the results of bacteriological studies conducted in the clinic revealed very high antibiotic resistance among *Shigella* strains. The etiological cause was most often polyresistant strains of *Shigella sonnei* (76.0%) and *Shigella flexneri* (24.0%). Among 62 patients with dysentery, dysentery caused by *Shigella sonnei* was diagnosed in 75% of cases. The spectrum of concomitant diseases is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Number and structure of concomitant diseases in dysentery

Concomitant diseases	Total patients, n=62	Total patients, n=62	Age of patients	Age of patients	Age of patients	Age of patients	P
Concomitant diseases	Total patients, n=62	Total patients, n=62	0-1 year, n=20	0-1 year, n=20	1-3 years, n=42	1-3 years, n=42	P
Concomitant diseases	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%	P
Anemia	30	48.4	10	50.0	20	64.5	>0.05
Nutritional disorders	18	29.0	8	40.0	10	23.8	>0.05
Rickets	21	33.8	9	45.0	12	28.5	>0.05
Exudative-catarrhal diathesis	14	22.6	2	10.0	12	28.5	<0.05
Perinatal encephalopathy	25	40.3	16	80.0	9	21.4	<0.001

The criteria for assessing the severity of the disease were: the acuity of development of the infectious process, the degree of severity of toxicosis and exsiccosis, the duration of the temperature reaction and gastrointestinal disorders, the degree of involvement of the cardiovascular and central nervous systems in the pathological process, and coprogram indicators.

Taking these criteria into account, a moderate form was diagnosed in 45 (72%) of the examined patients, and a severe form in 17 (28%).

The disease proceeded predominantly as gastroenterocolitis (59.7%) and hemocolitis (40.3%); moderate forms of the disease predominated in 72% (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of patients depending on severity and type of gastrointestinal lesion

Total patients	Moderate	Severe	Gastrointestinal lesions	Gastrointestinal lesions
Total patients	Moderate	Severe	Gastroenterocolitis	Hemocolitis
n = 62	45 72.6%	17 27.4%	37 59.7%	25 40.3%

Severe forms of dysentery were noted in 28% of children with the development of toxicosis and severe dehydration, with manifestations of convulsive syndrome and infectious-toxic shock of I and II degrees.

In the early stages of the disease, various symptoms were observed in children. In the majority (74.1%), fever above 38°C was noted, lasting on average about 3 days. Intoxication manifested in all patients as weakness and lethargy; in half of the patients it was accompanied by single vomiting, as well as decreased appetite (93.5%) and sleep disorders (59.6%). Among dyspeptic manifestations, abdominal pain (90.3%), bloating (54.8%), and rumbling in the intestines (33.8%) predominated. In most children (70.9%), spasm of the sigmoid colon was observed, and in a significant proportion (67.7%), anal compliance, tenesmus, and similar symptoms were noted.

No rectal prolapse was observed. All sick children had stool with pathological admixtures (mucus, pus, blood), with changes in consistency and frequency of more than 12-15 or more times per day.

In the moderate form of acute dysentery, in most children the disease began suddenly with a high temperature (38-39°C), which normalized by days 3-4. In a small proportion of patients (17%), no fever was observed. Intoxication, manifested by lethargy, decreased appetite, and single vomiting, was present in 60% of children. Mild or moderate dehydration (degree I-II) was detected in 8.6% of patients. Blood analysis showed moderate leukocytosis (up to 9-10•10⁹/L) with predominance of band neutrophils and a slight acceleration of ESR (14-15 mm/hour). Stool changes specific to dysentery (mucus, leukocytes, erythrocytes) were detected in one third of patients (34.3%). Dysbacteriosis was noted in all children (100%). The characteristics of the main symptoms of acute dysentery depending on etiology are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of the main symptoms of dysentery in children depending on etiology

Clinical signs	Etiology of dysentery	Etiology of dysentery	Etiology of dysentery
Clinical signs	Shigella sonnei (n=47)	Shigella flexneri (n=15)	P
Duration of fever:	2.5±1.15	3.0±1.18	>0.05
- Subfebrile	22 (46.8%)	6 (40.%)	>0.05
- High	20 (42.5%)	4 (26.6%)	>0.05
Duration of diarrhea	7.9±6.28	10.0±0.87	>0.05
Duration of abdominal pain	4.3±2.42	4.56±2.3	>0.05
- Stool frequency up to 10 times	21 (44.6%)	5 (33.3%)	>0.05
- Stool frequency more than 10 times	26 (55.3%)	10 (66.7%)	>0.05
Weakness, lethargy	47 (100.0%)	13 (86.6%)	<0.05
Appetite disturbance	44 (93.6%)	14 (93.3%)	>0.05
- Coprogram changes: mucus, leukocytes,	28 (44.4%)	11 (65.7%)	>0.05

erythrocytes in large quantities;			
- Mucus and leukocytes in large quantities, isolated erythrocytes;	35 (88.9%)	11 (33.3%)	>0.05
- Mucus, isolated leukocytes	21 (34.3%)	14 (22.3%)	<0.001

A severe form of dysentery was observed in a significant proportion of children. In 17 of the 62 examined children (27.4%), the disease proceeded in a severe form.

Onset of the disease and general symptoms:

- Acute onset: In most children (58.8%), the disease began suddenly with a sharp increase in body temperature to high values. In a smaller proportion of children (41.2%), the temperature was moderately elevated (subfebrile).
- General condition: The general well-being of the children was severely impaired.
- Toxicosis: In the overwhelming majority of patients (76.4%), severe toxicosis developed, manifested by drowsiness and general weakness (adynamia). In 8 children (47%), convulsions in the form of small muscle twitching were observed.
- Dehydration: In more than half of the children (58.8%), moderate dehydration (degree II) was noted.

Bacteriologically, intestinal dysbacteriosis of varying degrees was confirmed in all cases. Of these:

- Degree I was diagnosed in 14% (22.6%) of patients.
- Degree II was diagnosed in 36% (58.0%) of patients.
- Degree III was diagnosed in 12% (19.4%) of patients.

In most cases (62.5%), dysbacteriosis was caused by a deficiency of lactobacilli and bifidobacteria, and in 37.5% of cases by an increased content of hemolytic *Escherichia coli*. The presence of lactose-negative *Escherichia coli* in quantities exceeding 10% of the total number of normal *Escherichia coli* was also noted. In most cases, the patient's own microflora did not possess sufficient antibacterial activity. A pronounced decrease in the number of bifidobacteria and lactobacilli contributed to further disruption of the intestinal microflora composition, an increase in the number of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria, and the growth of opportunistic microorganisms.

The study of children admitted to the hospital during the first day of illness showed:

- In most children (75%), bifidoflora was either completely absent or significantly reduced already upon admission. This may indicate pre-existing disturbances of intestinal microflora.
- Among 21 children who achieved clinical recovery, 20 showed a tendency toward an increase in the number of bifidobacteria.
- In 12 children on artificial feeding who suffered from recurrent dysentery, a persistently low level of bifidobacteria (10^2 - 10^4 mc/g) was noted.
- It is important to note that clinical recovery does not always coincide with restoration of the normal level of intestinal bifidoflora. Assessment of the content of lactobacilli was carried out upon admission (days 1-2) and during the recovery period (after 7-10 days):

In two thirds of the children (2/3), lactoflora remained in large quantities (10^6 mc/g and higher).

In 20.9% of children, the level of lactobacilli was within the lower limit of the norm (10^5 - 10^6 mc/g).

A decrease in the number of lactobacilli was recorded in only 11.6% of patients.

During the development of dysentery, an increase in the number of children with a high content of lactobacilli (more than 10^6 mc/g) was observed, reaching 81.4%.

Quantitative changes in lactobacterial flora in acute dysentery in children are less pronounced than changes in bifidoflora.

Associated dysbacteriosis was detected in 26.6% of cases. When 1-2 types of opportunistic microflora and fungi of the genus *Candida* were detected, prolonged disturbances of intestinal function were noted, and intestinal dysbacteriosis of degrees II-III was also diagnosed more often.

Clinical observations indicate that in patients with acute dysentery occurring against the background of intestinal dysbacteriosis of degrees II-III:

- Normalization of stool occurs later (on average after 15.4 ± 2.5 days).
- Abdominal pain (on average 10.0 ± 1.9 days), meteorism (on average 10.5 ± 1.8 days), and coated tongue (on average 21.4 ± 2.5 days) persist longer.
- Signs of anemia were also detected significantly more often.

Conclusion

Thus, these data confirm that dysentery in children has now begun to proceed more severely, with prolonged recovery (3-4 weeks) and a tendency toward relapse. Resistance of pathogens to antibiotics is noted. Combined lesions of the gastrointestinal tract (gastroenterocolitis, hemocolitis), pronounced pain and colitic syndromes, prolonged fever, moderate dehydration, as well as convulsions and neurotoxicosis are frequently observed. Changes in the intestinal microflora are considered a factor aggravating the course of the disease.

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